

THE EFFECT OF DIALECTS ON IMPERATIVE FORMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Annotation: This study explores the effect of dialectal variations on imperative forms in English and Uzbek. Dialects influence the structure, usage, and politeness levels of imperative sentences, shaping communication styles across different regions. In English, imperative construction varies in formality and directness depending on dialectal differences, such as those found in British, American, and regional English varieties. Similarly, Uzbek dialects exhibit unique imperative structures and politeness markers, distinguishing formal and informal speech.

Keywords: dialects, imperative forms, English, Uzbek, Linguistic variation, regional differences, speech patterns, politeness strategies, sociolinguistics, cross-linguistic comparison. The morphological category is one of the most important characteristics of a part of speech, i.e., a whole class of words. A part of speech is always expressed by a particular word with its lexical meaning. Dialectal differences significantly influence the structure and usage of imperative forms in both English and Uzbek. In English, commands and requests vary based on regional dialects, affecting politeness, directness, and verb structure. Similarly, in Uzbek, dialectal variations impact the formation of alternative expressions for addressing different social groups. This paper explores how dialectal diversity shapes imperative usage in these two languages. Saussure says: "in language [langue] there are only differences, while Stephen Krashen said: "the optimal way a language is learned is through natural communication. As a second language teacher, the ideal is to create a situation wherein language is used in order to fulfill an authentic purpose. This, in turn, will help students to acquire the language instead of just learning "it". Many foreign scholars are engaged in problems in studying the system of modality in English and Uzbek and its specific methodological aspects and effective ways to apply them in oral and

written speech and in the analysis of the theory of modal relations in English linguistics in particular, Vinogradov V.V, Serebrennikov B.A, Yarseva V.N, Barkhudarov L.S studied language families approaching them comparatively. It is clear from their research that despite the huge differences between the two language families, they have many similarities and differences. Dialectal differences play a crucial role in shaping the imperative forms in both English and Uzbek. In English regional dialects influence the tone formality and structure of commands, with variations in politeness strategies across American, British and other varieties. Dialects also exhibit diverse imperative forms with some regions incorporating additional suffixes or alternative expressions to soften commands or show respect. This study examines how dialects impact the imperative mood in both languages considering syntactic, morphological and pragmatic perspectives.

INTRODUCTION: Languages is not static; it evolves through time and varies across regions. One of the linguistic aspects influenced by dialectal difference is the imperative mood, which is used to give commands, make requests, or offer suggestions. In both English and Uzbek, the way imperatives are expressed can change based on dialects, cultural expectations, and levels of politeness. English dialects often modify imperative structure by adjusting politeness strategies, while Uzbek dialects influence imperatives through verb morphology and honorific expression. This paper examines how dialectal variations affect imperative forms in both languages, comparing structural, pragmatic and sociolinguistic factors.

Imperative Forms and Their Characteristics: The imperative mood is used to express commands instructions, request, or advice. In both English and Uzbek, imperative are usually structured using the base form of the verb.

1. English: "Close the door." / "Please sit down."

Uzbek: "Eshikni yop." / "O'tiring."

2. English: "Turn off the light." / "Please, turn off the light."

Uzbek: "Chiroqlarni o'chir." / "Iltimos chiroqlarni o'chiring."

3. English: "Come here ." / "Could you come here ,please?"

Uzbek: "Bu yerga kel." / "Iltimos bu yerga keeling."

However, the degree of politeness, formality, and directness can vary significantly depending on dialects and cultural norms. Dialectal Variations in English Imperative Forms: English is spoken across different regions and each dialect has unique ways of forming imperative. Some key variations include.

British English and American English:

British English often uses indirect forms for politeness: "Would you mind closing the window?"

American English tends to be more direct: "Close the window, please."

These variations highlight how dialects shape the way imperatives are expressed in English. Dialectal Variations in Uzbek Imperative Forms: Uzbek dialects also influence imperative forms in various ways. Some notable differences include:

Toshkent dialect and Samarkand Dialect:

Toshkent dialect often uses softer commands: "Kelavering."

Samarkand dialect may use more direct forms: "Keling!"

Imperative Mood of English Language. Verbs in the form of the imperative mood express the urge to perform an action: command, offer, request, etc. The subject is absent in such sentences, and the predicate is used in the form of an infinitive without "to". Usually, an order, offer or request is addressed to a second person (you, you) or to a group of people, for example: Give me the salt, please! Tuzni olib bering! Bring me the book. Kitobni menga olib keling! Open the door and air the room! Oynani oching va xonani shamollating! In order to express the prohibition to commit an action related to the 2nd person, the negation "don't (= do not)" is put before the verb in the form of the imperative mood: Don't make noise here! Bu yerda shovqin qilmang! Don't cross the street here! Bu ko'chani kesib o'tmang! As in Uzbek, the order can be addressed to a third party, for example: Bolalar uyga boraqolsin (borsin). Let the children go home. Madina idishni yuvsin(yuva qolsin). Let Madina wash up. In this case, the motivation for action is expressed using the service verb "let", followed by a noun or pronoun denoting the person to whom this motivation refers, and the verb in the infinitive form without "to". Moreover, pronouns are used in the form of an indirect case (him, her, them). For example: Let her come in. Uni(qiz bola)kirishiga ruxsat berin. Let him open the window. Uni (o'g'il bola) oynani ochishiga ruxsat berin. When calling for joint action, after the verb "let" the pronoun "us" (let us = let's) is used, which translates into Uzbek as "keling, qani ". When the speaker expresses his desire to perform the action himself, the pronoun "me" is used after the verb "let". For instance: Let us play volleyball! Qani,(Keling) voleybol oynaymiz! Let's go to the cinema tonight. Keling (Qani)bugun kechga kinoga boramiz! Let me do it myself. Buni o'zim qilishimga ijozat(ruxsat) bersangiz. In order to express the prohibition to perform an action, the negation "don't (do not)" is placed before the service verb

"let": Don't let my brother read the letter! Akam xatni o'qishiga yo'l qo'ymang! Don't let him smoke here! Uni bu yerda chekishiga yo'l qo'ymang! (ruxsat bermang!) 2. Imperative-Subjunctive mood of Uzbek language. Imperative-subjunctive mood expresses command, and desire, urge, please in the process of performing an action. For example: Listen carefully to what your father says! Please, pay attention to next exercise! Addressing to the second person of the imperative-subjunctive mood means a firm command: For example: Are you ready? So, take the load into a lorry. It refers to ask positive request, to please, and to urge. Such as, We will be on the way to Fergana. Let my mother know about it. (P.Q.) Addressing to the third person of the imperative-subjunctive mood basically means the real command, as well as when it is said in a calm tone, it expresses please and urge like: Do not hurry, let them come out; Let's take a break. (O.Yo.) 3. Subjunctive mood of English language. The subjunctive mood (Istak mayl) denotes actions that could occur in imaginary (unreal) situations. It is used: 1. In the subordinate clauses after the verbs suggest-(taklif qilmoq), demand / require – (talab qilmoq), insist – (qattiq turib olmoq), order – (buyurmoq), etc. By the form it coincides with the infinitive without a particle to (Subjunctive I) or is expressed by the combination: should + infinitive I suggest (ed) (that) he should cancel the meeting. I suggest (suggested) that he cancel the meeting. The director ordered that the equipment (should) be shipped immediately. The director ordered the equipment to be loaded immediately. 2. After adjectives desirable - desirable, doubtful – (shubhali), essential – (muhim), important – (zarur,muhim) necessary –(kerakli), etc. in construction: It is + adj. + that : It is important (that) you (should) be here. Siz shu yerda bo'lishingiz muhimdir. It is necessary (that) the equipment (should) be repaired as soon as possible. Bu jihoz imkon boricha tezroq ta'mirlanishi muhim sanaladi. The conditional mood is an action that is conditional on the performance of an action. The conditional tense form of the verb of uzbek language grammar is formed by adding and subtracting the suffix "sa" to the base of the verb.

Therefore, the suffix „sa“ is a conditional mood form of the verb.

- 1 Person : If I write (Agar yozsam)
- 2 Person : If you write (Agar yozsang)
- 3. Person : If they write (Agar yozsalar)

The conditional tense form represents the meaning as follows.

A) A speech represents an action that must be performed before the time it is spoken.

This form is formed by the suffix -sa and the incomplete verb of uzbek grammar “edi”:

If only I did it.

I wish I went to party.

B) Represents an action happened in the speech process.

This form is expressed by the suffix -sa, and the verb that takes this suffix comes as a part of the subordinate clause:

If a picture is found in her house, it is blamed on the girl. (P.Q.)

Agar rasm uning uyida topilsa, bunda qizni ayblashadi.

C) Represents the purpose, dream, desire. This form is formed by adding the suffix -sa to the verb, as well as conjugating the verb by adding the suffix –sa to the verb of subordinate clause. For example, if I say (Aytsam); If I go(Borsam), If I come(Kelsam).

As a result of the research the following conclusions and recommendations can be formed:

- a) the syntax and modal verbs of the foreign language are studied comparing them with the first language when learning the moods from the grammar of it ;
- b) when mastering the subject of the category of moods of a foreign language, one should take into account its various meanings and apply them correctly in practice;
- d) It is important to pay attention to the context in distinguishing the singular from the plural of a modal verb in a foreign language.

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